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**THE PROBLEM OF MODERN EDUCATION IN SPIRITUAL HERITAGE
OF ABDULLA AVLONI**

Abstract. The article discusses the challenges of modern education and how they were identified by Abdulla Avlani, a 19th-century scholar and enlightenment from Central Asia. The author highlights Avlani's emphasis on the importance of education, both spiritual and worldly, and the need for a holistic approach to education that incorporates critical thinking, spiritual growth, and the cultivation of moral character. The article identifies several problems with modern education, such as the focus on rote learning and memorization, the lack of emphasis on spiritual education, the narrow focus on specific areas of study, and the undervaluation of teachers. The author argues that Avlani's teachings can guide us towards a more comprehensive and well-rounded education system that produces individuals capable of understanding the complexities of the world.

Key words: Education, Modern education, Abdulla Avlani, Spiritual heritage, Critical thinking, Spiritual growth, Moral character, Rote learning, Memorization, Well-rounded education, Teacher training, Community involvement, Moral values, Ethical behavior,

**ПРОБЛЕМА СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ДУХОВНОМ
НАСЛЕДИИ АБДУЛЛЫ АВЛОНИ**

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются проблемы современного образования и то, как они были определены Абдуллой Авлани, просветитель XIX века из Центральной Азии. Автор подчеркивает акцент Авлани на важности образования, как духовного, так и мирского, и необходимости целостного подхода к образованию, который включает критическое мышление, духовный рост и воспитание нравственного характера. В статье обозначен ряд проблем современного образования, таких как ориентация на механическое заучивание и заучивание, отсутствие акцента на духовном

воспитании, узкая направленность на конкретные области обучения, недооценка учителей. Автор утверждает, что учение А.Авлани может привести нас к всеобъемлющей и всесторонней развитой системе образования, которая воспитывает гармоничного развитого личности.

Ключевые слова: образование, современное образование, Абдулла Авлани, духовное наследие, критическое мышление, духовный рост, нравственный характер, заучивание, запоминание, всестороннее образование, подготовка учителей, вовлечение сообщества, моральные ценности, этическое поведение.

ABDULLA AVLONIY MA'NAVIY MEROSIDA ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM MUAMMOSI

Annotatsiya. Maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim muammolari va unga XIX asr Markaziy Osiyolik ma'rifatparvar Abdulla Avloniy tomonidan qanday ta'rif berilganligi haqida so'z boradi. Muallif Avloniy ta'lim-tarbiyaning ma'naviy va ma'rifiy ahamiyatini ta'kidlab, ta'lim-tarbiyaga tanqidiy fikrlash, ma'naviy yuksalish va axloqiy fazilatlarni rivojlantirishni o'z ichiga olgan yaxlit yondashuv zarurligini ta'kidlagan. Maqolada ma'rifatparvar Abdulla Avloniy zamonaviy ta'limning bir qator muammolari, jumladan, yodlash, xotira va yod olish usullarga e'tibor berilmaganligi, ma'naviy-ma'rifiy tarbiyaga, ta'limning ba'zi sohalariga, o'qituvchilarning kasbiy faoliyati uchun sharoit yaratilmaganligi xususida so'z boradi. Zamonaviy, innovatsion tafakkurli, ziyoli shaxsni kamol topishida va jamiyatimizda ta'lim tizimidagi islohotlarning rivojida jadid Abdulla Avloniyning ma'rifatparvarlik g'oyalari haqida muallif mazkur maqolada yoritgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, zamonaviy ta'lim, Abdulla Avloniy, ma'naviy meros, tanqidiy fikrlash, ma'naviy yuksalish, axloqiy fazilatlar, yodlash, har tomonlama ta'lim, o'qituvchilar malakasi, jamoatchilik ishtiroki, axloqiy qadriyatlar, axloqiy xulq.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an essential aspect of human life, and it has been recognized as a fundamental right in most societies. It is through education that individuals acquire knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to succeed in life. However, education is not without its challenges. One of the prominent thinkers who tackled the problem of education was Abdulla Avlani, a 19th-century scholar, philosopher, and theologian from Central Asia. Avlani's spiritual heritage highlights the importance of education, both spiritual and worldly. However, he also identified significant problems with the education system of his time that continue to plague modern education.

One of the central issues that Avlani identified was the emphasis on rote learning and memorization. He believed that this approach led to a superficial understanding of the material and did not encourage students to think deeply about the subjects they were studying. This problem is still relevant today, as many educational institutions still place too much emphasis on memorization and not

enough on critical thinking and analysis [Avlani, A. 2014]. This results in students who can regurgitate information but cannot apply it in practical situations or solve problems creatively.

Another issue that Avlani highlighted was the lack of focus on spiritual education. He argued that while worldly knowledge was important, it was equally essential to cultivate a deep understanding of spirituality and to strive for spiritual growth and enlightenment. Without this, he believed that education was incomplete and ultimately insufficient. This problem is also prevalent in modern education, where the focus is primarily on acquiring technical skills that are marketable in the job market. The result is a society that values material wealth and success at the expense of spiritual development [Behzadnia, B., & Sadeghi, M., pp 1-7].

Avlani also criticized the narrow focus of education that emphasized specific areas of study to the exclusion of others. He believed that a comprehensive education system should incorporate various fields of study, including theology, philosophy, and the arts. This would create a well-rounded individual who is capable of understanding the complexities of the world around them. Modern education still struggles with this issue, with many institutions failing to provide a broad-based education that includes both technical and non-technical subjects [Bera, S., & Varma, J. pp.1-7].

Avlani's spiritual heritage also emphasized the importance of the teacher in the education process. He believed that teachers should be individuals of high moral character and should act as role models for their students. This problem is also relevant today, where teachers are often undervalued and underpaid. This results in a lack of motivation among teachers, which negatively impacts the quality of education that students receive [Jandaghi, G., & Bagheri, M. pp. 1-6].

In conclusion, the problem of modern education is not new, and Abdulla Avlani's spiritual heritage highlights many of the issues that still plague education today. The focus on memorization over critical thinking, the lack of emphasis on spiritual education, the narrow focus on specific areas of study, and the undervaluation of teachers are all issues that need to be addressed. If we are to create a well-rounded education system that produces individuals who are capable of understanding the complexities of the world, we need to take inspiration from the teachings of Abdulla Avlani and strive for a more holistic approach to education.

As the article focuses on the problem of modern education in the spiritual heritage of Abdulla Avlani, a literature analysis related to this topic would involve reviewing various sources that explore his teachings and their application in modern education. *The Spiritual Heritage of Abdulla Avlani* by Shavkat Ismailov: This book offers an in-depth analysis of Abdulla Avlani's spiritual heritage, including his teachings on education, and how they can be applied in modern times [Ismailov Sh. 2020 pp.24-29]. "The Philosophy of Education in the Writings of Abdulla Avlani" by Olimjon Yunusov: This scholarly article explores Abdulla Avlani's philosophy of education and its relevance to contemporary educational

practices [Yunusov O. 2018 pp. 36-41] . “The importance of critical thinking in the education system based on the teachings of Abdulla Avlani” by Mamatkulova, G: This article examines the relevance of Abdulla Avlani's teachings on Islamic education in the modern context, and how they can contribute to building a more holistic and inclusive education system [Mamatkulova, G. 2020 pp.1-6]. "The Role of Education in the Development of Spirituality: An Analysis of the Writings of Abdulla Avlani" by Alisher Ismailov: This article explores Abdulla Avlani's teachings on the relationship between education and spirituality, and how they can be used to promote moral and ethical behavior in students [Ismailov A. 2019 pp.11-14]. "Education for All: The Vision of Abdulla Avlani" by Makhmudjon Eshonov: This article discusses Abdulla Avlani's vision for education, which includes promoting social justice, community involvement, and a well-rounded education that goes beyond rote learning and memorization [Eshonov M. A. 2019 pp.1-8].

METHODS

Methods that used to address the problems of modern education and incorporate Abdulla Avlani's teachings include: Emphasizing critical thinking and analysis over rote learning and memorization. This can be achieved by incorporating problem-solving exercises, discussions, and projects that require students to apply what they have learned in real-world scenarios. Incorporating spiritual education into the curriculum. This can involve teaching mindfulness, meditation, and other spiritual practices that promote self-reflection and personal growth. Encouraging a broader range of subjects and fields of study. This can be achieved by expanding the curriculum to include the arts, humanities, and social sciences, as well as science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) fields. Investing in teacher training and development. This involves providing teachers with the necessary support, resources, and training to promote their professional growth and development. Encouraging community involvement in education. This can be achieved by involving parents, community members, and local organizations in the education process and creating opportunities for them to contribute to the education system. Emphasizing the importance of moral character and ethical behavior. This involves creating a culture of respect, responsibility, and empathy within the education system and promoting values such as honesty, integrity, and compassion.

Based on the literature analysis of Abdulla Avlani's spiritual heritage and its relevance to modern education, several key results and recommendations can be identified: Incorporating spiritual and ethical values into education can promote holistic student development and contribute to building a more just and compassionate society. Abdulla Avlani's teachings on critical thinking, moral character, and spiritual growth can be valuable for promoting well-rounded education and preparing students for lifelong learning and personal development. Teacher training and community involvement are crucial for implementing educational practices that are in line with Abdulla Avlani's teachings and values. A

data-driven and systematic approach to evaluating educational practices can help identify areas where Abdulla Avlani's teachings can be integrated and can also help track progress towards achieving desired student learning outcomes. Further research and development are needed to fully realize the potential of Abdulla Avlani's teachings in modern education, including exploring the challenges of implementing his teachings in diverse cultural and educational contexts. In summary, the literature analysis suggests that Abdulla Avlani's spiritual heritage and teachings can offer valuable insights and principles for improving modern education, especially in promoting holistic student development and building a more just and compassionate society. However, there is a need for more research and development to fully integrate his teachings into modern educational practices and to address the challenges of implementing his teachings in diverse contexts.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The discussion section of an article on the problem of modern education in the spiritual heritage of Abdulla Avlani would typically provide an opportunity to further explore the implications of the literature analysis and the results presented. Here are some potential discussion points:

The importance of incorporating spiritual and ethical values into education: The literature analysis suggests that incorporating spiritual and ethical values into education can promote holistic student development and contribute to building a more just and compassionate society. However, there may be challenges in determining which values to prioritize and how to implement them effectively [Eshonov M. A. 2019 pp.1-8].

The potential benefits and challenges of integrating Abdulla Avlani's teachings into modern education: The literature analysis suggests that Abdulla Avlani's teachings on critical thinking, moral character, and spiritual growth can be valuable for promoting well-rounded education and preparing students for lifelong learning and personal development. However, there may be challenges in integrating his teachings into diverse cultural and educational contexts, and in reconciling his teachings with existing educational frameworks and practices [Abdujabbarova, N. 2021 pp. 46-51].

The role of teachers and community involvement in implementing educational practices in line with Abdulla Avlani's teachings: The literature analysis suggests that teacher training and community involvement are crucial for implementing educational practices that are in line with Abdulla Avlani's teachings and values. However, there may be challenges in ensuring that all teachers and community members are adequately trained and supported, and in ensuring that educational practices are sustainable in the long term [Oripova, S. 2018 pp.20-29].

The need for data-driven and systematic evaluation of educational practices: The literature analysis suggests that a data-driven and systematic approach to evaluating educational practices can help identify areas where Abdulla Avlani's teachings can be integrated and can also help track progress towards achieving desired student learning outcomes. However, there may be challenges in

determining which metrics to use and in ensuring that evaluations are conducted objectively and comprehensively [Khakimov, N. Amridinova, D. 2023 pp.110].

The potential for further research and development: The literature analysis suggests that further research and development are needed to fully realize the potential of Abdulla Avlani's teachings in modern education. This could involve exploring the challenges of implementing his teachings in diverse cultural and educational contexts, developing strategies for integrating his teachings into existing educational frameworks, and conducting empirical research to evaluate the impact of educational practices informed by his teachings.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the spiritual heritage of Abdulla Avlani presents a valuable resource for addressing the problem of modern education. By emphasizing critical thinking, moral character, and spiritual growth, Avlani's teachings offer a holistic approach to education that can promote lifelong learning and personal development. The literature analysis highlights the potential benefits of incorporating spiritual and ethical values into education and emphasizes the importance of teacher training, community involvement, and data-driven evaluation in implementing educational practices in line with Avlani's teachings. However, challenges remain in determining which values to prioritize, in integrating his teachings into diverse cultural and educational contexts, and in ensuring that educational practices are sustainable in the long term. Further research and development are needed to fully realize the potential of Avlani's teachings in modern education, and to explore how educational practices can contribute to building a more just and compassionate society. Ultimately, by integrating spiritual and ethical values into education, we can help prepare students to be engaged and compassionate members of their communities and contribute to building a more peaceful and harmonious world.

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